

Synergistic Growth of Giant Wormlike Micelles in Ternary Mixed Surfactant Solutions: Effect of Octanoic Acid

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Abstract

The synergistic growth of giant wormlike micelles in ternary mixed solutions comprised of an anionic surfactant (sodium laurylesulfate, SLES); a zwitterionic surfactant (cocamidopropyl betaine, CAPB), and octanoic acid (HC8), is studied. Rheological data and their analysis in terms of Cole-Cole plots and micellar characteristic times are presented and, in addition, the micellar structures behind the observed rheological behavior are revealed by cryo-TEM micrographs. The surfactant composition is fixed near the maximal micelle size of the binary SLES+CAPB system, whereas the concentration of HC8 is varied. At a given HC8 concentration, the viscosity of the ternary micellar solutions exhibits a very high and sharp peak. Polarized-light optical microscopy indicates that all investigated solutions are isotropic, rather than liquid-crystalline. The cryo-TEM imaging shows a complex phase behavior: wormlike micelles to the left of the peak; giant entangled wormlike micelles at the peak; and long wormlike micelles co-existing with multiconnected micellar aggregates to the right of the peak. The formation of multiconnected micelles leads to a drop in viscosity at the higher concentrations. The results contribute to a better understanding of the structure–rheology relations in micellar surfactant solutions and could be useful for controlling the properties of formulations in personal-care and house-hold detergency.

Keywords: wormlike micelles; micellar growth; viscosity peak; viscoelasticity; cryo-TEM.

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TOC Graph

1. Introduction

Slightly above the critical micelle concentration (CMC), surfactants form spherical micelles and the viscosity of their solutions is close to that of water. However, in the presence of electrolytes or co-surfactants, amphiphilic molecules can assemble into wormlike micelles or “living polymers”.¹ Above a certain micellar volume fraction, the worms intertwine and form a transient micellar network, which gives rise to viscoelastic behavior. In fundamental aspect, the relation between structure and rheology of concentrated micellar solutions has attracted considerable attention.²⁻¹³ In applied aspect, formulations containing wormlike micelles are frequently used as thickeners in cosmetics and homecare,¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and even as drug-delivery vehicles in biomedicine.¹⁵

In the numerous studies on concentrated micellar solutions, one could find many different ways to form wormlike micelles. Among them, the most common worm-forming systems consist of (i) an ionic surfactant and salt or hydrotrope;^{2-4,13,17-26} (ii) an ionic surfactant with nonionic and/or zwitterionic additives;²⁷⁻³⁵ (iii) two oppositely charged surfactants;³⁶⁻⁴¹ (iv) nonionic, gemini or biological surfactants;⁴²⁻⁴⁸ and (v) surfactant and co-surfactant.⁴⁹⁻⁵³ An extensive list of formulations containing wormlike micelles can be found in ref. 15.

Many worm-forming surfactant solutions show complex phase behavior and non-monotonic trends in their viscoelastic properties. Rehage and Hoffmann^{2,3} were among the first to demonstrate that the addition of salts or hydrotropes to cationic surfactant solutions induces micellar growth, and the zero-shear viscosity passes through one or even two peaks as a function of the concentration of additive. Similar non-monotonic rheological behavior was later observed in many other surfactant systems.^{4,13,18-24,29-35,38-40,42,44-46} The viscosity typically increases due to a transition from spherical to elongated and then to wormlike micelles. With the increase of surfactant concentration, the wormlike micelles intertwine and form a transient network, which leads to a considerable rise in viscosity.

However, in many systems the viscosity decreases at higher concentrations of the additive, which is counterintuitive. Summary of the different pathways explaining the viscosity reduction were first presented in ref. 40 and were further expanded in ref. 54. Three of the possible mechanisms are: (1) *micellar branching* – formation of dynamic connections between micelles, which can either slide along the micelle, or form 4-fold ghost-like crossings;^{11,12,55,56}

(2) *micellar shortening* – the micelles diminish in size at higher concentrations of the additive, which is especially common in catanionic mixtures,^{14,22,40} and (3) *shape or phase transition* – worms transform into discs, or isotropic micellar solutions are converted into liquid-crystalline mesophases.⁵⁷ To reveal the mechanism of viscosity reduction in a given system, direct cryo-TEM imaging should be applied.

Our goal in the present article is to examine the rheology–structure relations for ternary mixed micellar solutions, which contain a zwitterionic surfactant (cocamidopropyl betaine, CAPB), an anionic surfactant (sodium laurylethersulfate, SLES), and a nonionic co-surfactant (octanoic acid, HC8). From both fundamental and applied viewpoint, such systems are interesting since they exhibit a high and sharp peak of viscosity as a function of fatty acid concentration, which could be applied to control the rheological properties of shampoo-like formulations. To reveal the relations between the complex rheological behavior and the microstructure evolution, we employed cryogenic TEM.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we give a brief overview of the theory used in the subsequent analysis of the rheological results. Section 3 provides information about the materials and experimental methods used. In Section 4, the experimental results are presented and discussed. Special attention is paid to the relation between microstructure and rheology.

2. Theoretical Background

The rheological properties of wormlike micelles (or “living polymers”) in the semi-dilute regime are often described by Cates’ model.⁵⁻⁹ In this model, the stress relaxation mechanisms include: (i) *reptation* (moving like a snake in long grass) denotes the curvilinear diffusion of a wormlike micelle between the neighboring micelles⁵⁸ and (ii) *reversible scission* – the ability of the micelles to break and recombine. The overall rheological response is governed by the ratio $\zeta = \tau_{\text{break}} / \tau_{\text{rep}}$ of the characteristic breaking time τ_{break} to the characteristic time for reptation τ_{rep} . Provided that $\tau_{\text{break}} \ll \tau_{\text{rep}}$, i.e. $\zeta \ll 1$, such wormlike micellar solutions behave as Maxwellian fluids with a single relaxation time τ_{R} given by:^{5,6}

$$\tau_{\text{R}} \cong (\tau_{\text{break}} \tau_{\text{rep}})^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Under oscillatory shear, the storage G' and loss G'' moduli for a Maxwellian viscoelastic body obey the relationships:⁵⁹

$$G' = \frac{\omega^2 \tau_R^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_R^2} G_0, \quad G'' = \frac{\omega \tau_R}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_R^2} G_0 \quad (2)$$

where ω is the angular frequency of oscillations; and G_0 is the high-frequency plateau value of the elastic modulus. In the Maxwell model, the absolute value of the complex viscosity $|\eta^*|$ is given by the expression:⁵⁹

$$|\eta^*| = \frac{G_0 \tau_R}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2 \tau_R^2}} \quad (3)$$

Let ω_c be the crossover frequency, at which $G' = G''$. The latter equality, along with eq 2, implies that $\omega_c \tau_R = 1$; hence, $\tau_R = 1/\omega_c$ and $G_0 = 2G'$ at the crossover point. Having determined both G_0 and τ_R , one can calculate the zero-frequency viscosity $\eta_{\omega=0}$ as well as the correlation length ξ :^{2,3,6,59}

$$\eta_{\omega=0} = G_0 \tau_R, \quad \xi \approx \left(\frac{k_B T}{G_0} \right)^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

The expression for $\eta_{\omega=0}$ follows from eq 3; ξ characterizes the mesh size of the transient micellar network. Using eq 2, one can check that G' and G'' satisfy the equation:

$$(G' - G_{\text{osc}})^2 + G''^2 = G_{\text{osc}}^2 \quad (5)$$

where $G_{\text{osc}} = G_0/2$. This is an equation of circumference in the plane (G', G'') , which can be used to verify the validity of the Maxwell model by constructing a Cole-Cole plot (G'' vs G').^{8,9,17,59} For wormlike micellar solutions, however, deviations from the pure Maxwellian behavior typically occur at high frequencies and result in an upturn in the viscous modulus G'' .^{8,9,17} These phenomena can be explained as a transition in the relaxation mode from reptation to “breathing” or Rouse modes. To quantify the departure from the pure Maxwell model, Turner and Cates⁸ introduced the parameter:

$$\bar{\zeta} = \frac{\tau_{\text{break}}}{\tau_R}, \quad (6)$$

which can be determined by comparing numerical and experimental Cole-Cole plots (see below). Using eq 6 and the obtained $\bar{\zeta}$, one can estimate τ_{break} from purely viscoelastic data.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Materials. In the present study, we investigate the growth of giant micelles in ternary surfactant solutions. We studied a mixture of two surfactants and a co-surfactant (fatty acid), which are as follows: (i) a zwitterionic surfactant – cocamidopropyl betaine (CAPB), $M = 342.52$ g/mol, product of Goldschmidt GmbH – Germany with commercial name TEGO® Betain F50; (ii) an anionic surfactant – sodium laurylesulfate with one ethylene-oxide group (SLES-1EO or briefly SLES), $M = 332.43$ g/mol, product of Stepan Co., USA, with commercial name STEOL® CS-170 UB; and (iii) octanoic (caprylic) acid (HC8), $M = 144.21$ g/mol, product of Sigma-Aldrich – Germany. The structural formulae of the surfactants are given in Fig. 1. From the product specification data of TEGO® Betain F50, one sees that 100 mM CAPB contains from 81 to 120 mM NaCl. To determine the exact amount of NaCl in our batch, we performed electrolytic conductivity measurements (see Appendix A and Fig. S1) and found that 100 mM CAPB contains 118 ± 6 mM NaCl as an admixture.

All chemicals were used as received without further purification. The aqueous solutions were prepared with deionized water from an Elix® 3 water purification system (Merck Millipore, Merck KGaA, Germany).

3.2. Experimental section. The effect of HC8 on micellar growth was studied at fixed CAPB:SLES molar ratio equal to 7:3. The stock (binary) surfactant solution (CAPB:SLES = 7:3) was prepared in a reaction bottle and was homogenized on a magnetic stirrer at room temperature. Then, the dissolution of octanoic acid (HC8) into the mixed (binary) micelles was carried out at 70 – 75 °C by vigorous agitation on a temperature-controlled magnetic stirrer for at least 1.5 hours. The resulting ternary micellar solution was kept in a thermostat at 25 °C for 24 hours, so that chemical equilibrium could be reached. After that, the solutions were used for pH and rheological measurements, as well as for optical microscopy and cryo-TEM imaging.

3.3. Rheological Measurements. The rheological properties of the micellar solutions were characterized by a rotational rheometer (Bohlin Gemini, Malvern Instruments, UK) using cone-and-plate geometry with plate temperature ($T = 25$ °C) controlled by a Peltier unit. A

solvent trap was used to minimize the change in sample composition by evaporation during each measurement. For samples with zero-shear viscosity η_0 up to ca. 40 Pa·s we used a cone with diameter of 60 mm and a cone angle of 2° (the gap distance is 70 μm), whereas for samples with $\eta_0 > 40$ Pa·s we switched to a cone with diameter of 40 mm and a cone angle of 4° (the gap distance is 150 μm). Two types of rheological experiments were carried out: (i) steady shear and (ii) stress-controlled frequency sweep.

Figure 1. Structural formulae of the amphiphilic molecules used.

In the regime of *steady shear*, the shear stress σ was measured as a function of the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$ in the range from 0.01 to 10 s^{-1} . The apparent viscosity η and the zero-shear viscosity η_0 are defined as follows:

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = \frac{\sigma}{\dot{\gamma}}, \quad \eta_0 = \lim_{\dot{\gamma} \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sigma}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (7)$$

In the regime of *stress-controlled frequency sweep* (oscillatory deformation), the storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' , were measured as functions of the oscillation frequency $\nu = \omega/(2\pi)$ in

the range from 0.01 to 10 Hz at 2% amplitude of shear deformation that was in the range of the linear viscoelastic response of the studied samples.

3.4. Polarized-Light Optical Microscopy. This method was used to investigate the phase behavior of the surfactant solutions. To distinguish between isotropic (micellar) and birefringent (liquid-crystalline) media, we used Axioplan (Zeiss, Germany) optical microscope in transmitted-light polarization mode. The microscope was equipped with a polarizer, an analyzer and a compensator (retarder). In our case, the compensator was a first order retardation plate (λ -plate or red-I plate) positioned below the analyzer to improve visibility by introducing vivid interference colors. Birefringent specimens appeared iridescent with features that vary depending on overall shape and molecular order.⁶⁰ At the same conditions, isotropic (micellar) solutions were magenta-red in color without any distinguishable features.

3.5. Cryo-TEM Imaging. Specimens were prepared with a Vitrobot preparation unit (FEI Co., USA) at 25 °C and 100 % relative humidity. A drop of solution was placed on a holey carbon TEM grid and the excess liquid was blotted off with filter paper. The exact amount of blotting (repetitions and duration) was adjusted, so as to obtain films ranging in thickness between 100 and 250 nm.⁶¹ The blotted samples were kept in the Vitrobot for several seconds to relax from any shearing effects caused by the blotting procedure.⁶¹ The relaxed samples were then plunged into liquid ethane (−183 °C) to form vitrified specimens, which were stored in liquid nitrogen (−196 °C) until further inspection. Specimens were examined in a Tecnai F20 transmission electron microscope (FEI Co., USA) with integrated electron energy-loss spectrometer. The microscope operated at acceleration voltage of 200 kV using a Gatan cryo-specimen holder that maintained the vitrified specimens below −175 °C. To minimize the electron-beam radiation damage, we used the low-dose imaging mode of the microscope: the electron dose (always below 150 e/nm^2) was kept minimal, yet sufficient to record a micrograph. Micrographs were recorded digitally on a 2K CCD camera, using the DigitalMicrograph software.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Rheology in Steady Shear Regime. The basic surfactant solution consists of CAPB and SLES in 7:3 molar ratio. At this ratio and total surfactant (CAPB + SLES) concentration $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM, the natural pH is ca. 5.8 and the solution viscosity is maximal, $\eta_0 = 2.3$ mPa·s, due to synergistic growth of cylindrical micelles.⁶² In the present study, the focus is on the effect of fatty acid, which is added as a third component and is known to induce micellar growth.^{33,35,57}

Figure 2 presents our results from the steady shear experiments. The total surfactant concentration was fixed, $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM (70 mM CAPB + 30 mM SLES), whereas HC8 concentration was varied from 0 to 30 mM. Figure 2a shows the dependence of the apparent viscosity η on the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$. As seen in the figure, the low-viscosity solutions behave as quasi-Newtonian fluids. Thus, the solution, which contains 12 mM HC8, is practically Newtonian in the whole range of shear rates from 0.1 to 10 s⁻¹.

In contrast, as seen in Fig. 2a, at 15, 18 and 20 mM HC8, the solutions remain Newtonian up to a certain threshold shear rate $\dot{\gamma}_N$, but at $\dot{\gamma} > \dot{\gamma}_N$ shear-thinning is observed. The switch between Newtonian and shear-thinning behavior depends on the relaxation time τ_R and, as a rule, happens at lower $\dot{\gamma}_N$ for longer micelles. Indeed, at 18 mM HC8 and low shear rates the micellar solution is highly viscoelastic ($\eta_0 = 41.0$ Pa·s) and then η starts to decrease even at low shear rates $\dot{\gamma} \geq 0.1$ s⁻¹. Moreover, the rheological response at high shear rates, $\eta \propto \dot{\gamma}^{-1}$ at $\dot{\gamma} > \dot{\gamma}_N$, is characteristic for solutions of interweaved wormlike micelles.^{10,33,39}

Figure 2b shows the dependence of the zero-shear viscosity η_0 on HC8 concentration. Upon addition of HC8, η_0 passes through a sharp maximum at 18 mM HC8 reaching a maximal value of 41.0 Pa·s (Fig. 2b). The maximum is 4 orders of magnitude higher than the viscosity (2.3 mPa·s) of the binary micellar solution without octanoic acid. Similar sharp peak in viscosity (rapid growth) was recently reported³⁵ for the same surfactants, CAPB and SLES, in the presence of lauric acid (HC12).

Figure 2. Effect of octanoic acid (HC8) on the sample's viscosity at fixed $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM (70 mM CAPB and 30 mM SLES) – data from the steady shear regime. (a) Plot of the apparent shear viscosity η vs the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$. (b) The zero-shear viscosity η_0 vs HC8 concentration plotted in semi-log scale. The inset represents the same graph in linear scale.

Typically, such viscous mixtures are either isotropic micellar solutions or liquid-crystalline mesophases. To check whether liquid-crystalline structures are present in the investigated solutions (Fig. 2b), we used polarized-light optical microscopy and detected no birefringence. Hence, the ternary solutions are *isotropic* (micellar) up to 25 mM HC8. The pH of these micellar solutions decreases from 5.8 (no HC8) to about 5.1 (Fig. S2a). At higher HC8

concentrations, the solutions become turbid since the excess fatty acid cannot be solubilized in the mixed micelles and precipitates in the form of small droplets; see Fig. S2 and ref. 63. Above 25 mM HC8, the pH levels off, because the concentration of HC8 in the bulk is fixed to 4.2 mM, that is, the solubility of octanoic acid in water at 25 °C.⁶³

It should be noted that it is HC8, rather than sodium carboxylate (NaC8), which induces the micellar growth. Indeed, as shown in Fig. S2b, the degree of HC8 ionization in the mixed micelles is less than 4.5 %. Moreover, if we interchange HC8 with NaC8, the viscosity η_0 decreases (Fig. S3). The latter can be explained as follows: NaC8 increases the surface charge density of the mixed micelles. Hence, they diminish in size due to increased intramicellar electrostatic repulsion between the negatively-charged headgroups and η_0 drops. In contrast, the non-ionic HC8 decreases the surface charge density of the mixed micelles and serves as a spacer between the negatively-charged SLES headgroups, which leads to micellar growth.

Figure S4 shows our results from the steady shear experiments at $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ mM (140 mM CAPB + 60 mM SLES). We see that by increasing c_{tot} two times the zero-shear viscosity η_0 at the peak increases ca. 10 times: from 41.0 Pa.s at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM to 435 Pa.s at $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ mM. It should be noticed that the position of the peak shifts to the right from 18 mM HC8 at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM to 25 mM HC8 at $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ mM. Counterintuitively, the position of the peak does not change in proportion to the total surfactant (CAPB + SLES) concentration c_{tot} : one would expect the peak to be at 36 mM HC8, but in reality it is at 25 mM HC8. Therefore, we studied the effect of c_{tot} on the rheological behavior at fixed ratio, 7:3 CAPB/SLES, and fixed fatty acid concentration, 18 mM HC8, so that we always stay to the left from the viscosity peak.

In Fig. 3, we illustrate the effect of c_{tot} on the flow curves $\eta(\dot{\gamma})$ and on the zero-shear viscosity η_0 . The flow curves in Fig. 3a behave in a similar way to those in Fig. 2a: at high shear rates, $\eta \propto \dot{\gamma}^{-1}$ at $\dot{\gamma} > \dot{\gamma}_N$. To visualize the effect of the total surfactant concentration, in Fig. 3b we have plotted η_0 vs c_{tot} . We see that η_0 increases with the rise of c_{tot} , e.g., $\eta_0 = 426$ Pa·s at $c_{\text{tot}} = 400$ mM vs $\eta_0 \approx 41$ Pa·s at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM. As shown in Fig. 3b, the data obey power-law dependence, $\eta_0 \propto c_{\text{tot}}^{2.4}$. The exponent 2.4 is intermediate between the values 1–2 measured for multiconnected micelles¹² and the values 3.5–3.7 for one component wormlike micelles.^{6,17} Additional data for the shear stress vs shear rate can be found in Fig. S5.

Figure 3. Effect of the total surfactant concentration c_{tot} on the solution's viscosity at fixed octanoic acid (HC8) concentration. (a) Plot of the apparent shear viscosity η vs the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$. (b) The zero-shear viscosity η_0 vs c_{tot} ; the solid line is the best fit with power-law dependence, whereas the dashed line is a guide to the eye.

4.2. Rheology in Oscillatory Regime. Figure 4a shows plots of the storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' , versus the angular frequency ω at fixed shear-strain amplitude of 2 %. For all experimental curves, the molar ratio CAPB/SLES is equal to 7:3 and the concentration of fatty acid is fixed, 18 mM HC8; the total surfactant concentration is $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ and 400 mM for the respective pairs of curves. The investigated micellar solutions are viscoelastic; they are fluid-like

($G'' > G'$) at low frequencies and solid-like at high frequencies ($G' > G''$). From the crossing point ($G' = G''$), one can determine the crossover frequency ω_c and estimate the relaxation time $\tau_R = 1/\omega_c$; see Section 2.

To determine τ_R in a more reliable way, we simultaneously fitted $G'(\omega)$ and $G''(\omega)$ up to the crossing point using the Maxwell model described by eq 2; see the solid lines in Fig. 4a. The plateau modulus G_0 and the relaxation time τ_R were obtained as adjustable parameters from the fit. Analogous results for $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ and 300 mM can be found in Fig. S6. The obtained values of G_0 and τ_R are given in the second and third columns in Table 1. G_0 increases monotonically from 7.32 to 226 Pa as a function of c_{tot} , whereas τ_R decreases and reaches a plateau of ca. 2 s at the higher total surfactant concentrations. It is interesting to note that $G_0(c_{\text{tot}})$ follows a power-law dependence with an exponent of 2.5, which is in good agreement with the value of 2.3 ± 0.2 expected from refs. 6 and 17 as well as with the value of 2.25 determined in ref. 64.

Table 1. Rheological properties of the studied micellar solutions at fixed, 18 mM, HC8 concentration and varying total (CAPB+SLES) concentration c_{tot} .

c_{tot} (mM)	G_0 (Pa)	τ_R (s)	ξ (nm)	$\eta_{\omega=0}$ (Pa·s)	η_0 (Pa·s)	$\bar{\zeta}$	τ_{break} (s)
100	7.32	5.15	82.5	37.7	41.0	1.23	6.33
200	30.6	1.95	51.2	59.7	68.5	4.61	8.99
300	113	2.03	33.1	229	220	1.23	2.50
400	226	1.99	26.3	450	426	0.70	1.39

Using the values of G_0 and eq 4, we calculated the correlation length ξ , which is an estimate for the mesh size of the transient micellar network; see Table 1. ξ decreases about 3 times, from about 83 to 26 nm, as the wormlike micellar solutions become more concentrated. By substituting G_0 and τ_R in eq 4, we also estimated the zero-frequency viscosity $\eta_{\omega=0}$. In the fifth and sixth columns of Table 1, the values of $\eta_{\omega=0}$ and η_0 are compared. (η_0 is the plateau value of η at low $\dot{\gamma}$ obtained from the steady shear experiments; see above.) In all cases, $\eta_{\omega=0}$ and η_0 coincide within 12 %, which is known as Cox-Merz rule in the polymer literature.^{59,65}

Figure 4. Rheological data in oscillatory regime at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ and 400 mM (CAPB+SLES), at the same 18 mM HC8 concentration. (a) The storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' , vs the angular frequency ω ; the solid lines are drawn in accordance with the Maxwell model. (b) Cole-Cole plots of G''/G_{osc} vs G'/G_{osc} , where $G_{\text{osc}} = G_0/2$; the semicircle represents pure Maxwellian behavior, whereas the solid lines are fits of numerical data from refs. 8 and 17.

To obtain quantitative information about the stress relaxation mechanisms (breaking and reptation), we determined the parameter $\bar{\zeta}$, which is related to τ_{break} ; see eq 6. The procedure is as follows:

- (1) The experimental data are plotted in the dimensionless scale G''/G_{osc} vs G'/G_{osc} (a Cole-Cole plot). For pure Maxwellian behavior (see eq 5), the Cole-Cole plot represents a

semicircle of radius $G_{\text{osc}} = G_0/2$. If there are deviations from the semicircle, they typically occur at high frequencies (high G') and are quantified by $\bar{\zeta}$.

- (2) To determine $\bar{\zeta}$, the experimental Cole-Cole plots are compared to the theoretical Cole-Cole plots (for $\bar{\zeta} = 0.13, 0.38, 0.70, 1.23, 2.38, 4.61$ and 10.2) given in refs. 8 and 17.
- (3) From this comparison, the value of $\bar{\zeta}$ that best describes our rheological data is determined and $\tau_{\text{break}} = \bar{\zeta}\tau_{\text{R}}$ (see eq 6) is calculated.

Figure 4b presents the Cole-Cole plots for $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ and 400 mM. Analogous plots for $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ and 300 mM are given in Fig. S7. In Figs. 4b and S7, our rheological data (symbols) are compared with the theoretical Cole-Cole plots (solid lines) from refs. 8 and 17. From this comparison, the estimated values of $\bar{\zeta}$ are given in Table 1, where the last column contains the values of the characteristic time for reversible scission τ_{break} . In other words, we estimated τ_{break} from purely rheological data using Cates' model.⁸ (For concentrated surfactant systems, τ_{break} is difficult to measure directly via T-jump experiments.) Cates' model predicts that τ_{break} is inversely proportional to the average micellar length \bar{L} . Typically, $\bar{L} \propto (c_{\text{tot}})^{1/2}$; see, e.g., refs. 1 and 35. Hence, τ_{break} is expected to decrease with the rise of c_{tot} in agreement with the tendency of our data in Table 1.

4.3. Cryo-TEM Imaging. Cryogenic TEM was applied to obtain structure-specific information for the changes that occur in the investigated micellar solutions at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM and increasing HC8 concentration. At higher c_{tot} , the cryo-TEM imaging is cumbersome, mainly, for two reasons: (i) thin sample (below 250 nm) is difficult to prepare; and (ii) the micrographs become crowded due to overlapping micelles. Cryo-TEM micrographs were taken at the viscosity peak, 18 mM HC18, and on both sides of the peak, viz. at 15 and 20 mM HC8; see Fig. 2b.

Figure 5 shows typical cryo-TEM micrographs taken at 15 mM HC8, i.e. to the left of the peak, where the zero-shear viscosity is $\eta_0 = 496$ mPa·s. Under these conditions, long overlapping wormlike micelles are seen throughout the sample. The micelles are highly polydisperse in length, which is typical for cylindrical and wormlike aggregates. The solution's viscosity is nearly 500 times that of water, because the worms are hundreds of nanometers in length and have high length-to-thickness aspect ratio. Such elongated micelles can easily overlap and enhance the rheological response of the system.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Cryo-TEM micrographs at 15 mM HC8 (to the left from the viscosity peak); 70 mM CAPB; 30 mM SLES; $\eta_0 = 0.496$ Pa·s. (a) Long polydisperse wormlike micelles form a dense film of superimposed structures; 200 nm scale bar. (b) The wormlike micelles are hundreds of nanometers long with thickness up to 5–6 nm; 50 nm scale bar.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Cryo-TEM micrographs at 18 mM HC8 (at the viscosity peak); 70 mM CAPB; 30 mM SLES; $\eta_0 = 41.0$ Pa·s. (a) Giant interweaved wormlike micelles, which reach micrometer lengths, are observed on large areas of the grid; 500 nm scale bar. (b) The wormlike micelles are entangled, but they do not seem to form junctions and loops; 100 nm scale bar.

(a)

(b)

Figure. 7. Cryo-TEM micrographs at 20 mM HC8 (to the right from the viscosity peak); 70 mM CAPB; 30 mM SLES; $\eta_0 = 2.06$ Pa·s; 100 nm scale bars. (a) Long wormlike micelles organized in bundles; the areas with black dots represent cross-sections of such bundles. (b) Wormlike structures co-exist with multiconnected micelles and small rings.

Figure 6 shows micrographs taken at the viscosity peak, at 18 mM HC8, where the viscosity is $\eta_0 \approx 41,000$ mPa·s. Figure 6a represents a large area populated with giant intertwined wormlike micelles. Figures 6a and 6b show that the micelles reach micrometer lengths, so that their length-to-thickness aspect ratio exceeds 200. The latter is among the primary reasons for high solution's viscosity and gel-like structure since the worms start to entangle and form a transient micellar network.

It is important to note, however, that the micellar network is not interconnected – neither 3-fold and 4-fold junctions, nor loops are seen in Fig. 6b. All apparent crossing points are actually superimposed micelles from different planes, which overlap in the two-dimensional snapshot. Thus, it turns out that the sharp peak in viscosity (Fig. 2b) is due to the formation of giant intertwined wormlike micelles.

Figure 7 presents cryo-TEM micrographs taken at 20 mM HC8, i.e. to the right of the peak, where the viscosity is $\eta_0 = 2060$ mPa·s. One sees that (i) the wormlike micelles are organized in bundles (Fig. 7a); and (ii) the individual wormlike micelles co-exist with multiconnected micelles and small rings (loops); see Fig. 7b. Such structures as well as branched micelles, in general, are known to have additional stress relief mechanisms available, viz. fast and fluid sliding of branch points along the micelles, and ghost-like crossings at 4-fold junctions.^{11,12,55,56} These molecular mechanisms can explain the observed drop in viscosity to the right of the peak (Fig. 2b) as well as the rheological data in Table S1. It should be mentioned that branching in mixed systems is rather common and could be due to local inhomogeneities in the micelle composition.⁵⁴

5. Conclusions

In the present article, we investigated the synergistic growth of giant wormlike micelles in ternary mixed solutions, which consist of anionic (SLES), zwitterionic (CAPB) and non-ionic (HC8) surfactants. The effect of co-surfactant (HC8) on solution rheology and phase behavior was studied at fixed 7:3 CAPB/SLES molar ratio. Similarly to other worm-forming formulations,^{2-4,13,18-24,29-35,38-40,42,44-46} the viscosity of the mixtures η_0 follows a non-monotonic

trend. In our case, a sharp and high peak with $\eta_0 \approx 41,000$ mPa·s at 18 mM HC8 (Fig. 2b) was detected, which is 4 orders of magnitude greater than the viscosity of the binary surfactant solution without HC8.

Using optical microscopy in transmitted-light polarization mode, we did not detect any birefringence, which directly proves that all ternary solutions up to 25 mM HC8 are isotropic micellar, rather than liquid-crystalline. In contrast to a similar system studied in ref. 57, we can exclude the transition from isotropic micellar solution to liquid-crystalline phase as a probable explanation for the origin of the viscosity peak.

The steady state and oscillatory rheological experiments show that the investigated ternary micellar solutions are viscoelastic and obey the Maxwell viscoelastic model in a wide range of shear rates. At high rates of strain, the shear stress levels off (shear-banding) and $\eta \propto \dot{\gamma}^{-1}$, which is typical for solutions with intertwined wormlike micelles.^{10,33,39} However, shear-banding response and Maxwellian behavior have been also observed with solutions containing disclike micelles.⁵⁷ Therefore, to directly obtain structure-specific information and to identify the microstructures behind the non-monotonic rheological behavior, we employed cryogenic TEM.

The cryo-TEM imaging revealed complex phase behavior: wormlike micelles to the left of the peak; giant entangled wormlike micelles at the peak; and wormlike micelles co-existing with multiconnected micelles to the right of the peak. In mixed micellar solutions, multiconnected micelles could form due to local inhomogeneities in the micelle composition. Such multiconnected networks provide stress relief mechanisms analogous to those typical for branched micelles,^{11,12,55,56} whose formation is typically associated with the viscosity reduction to the right of the peak (Fig. 2b).

For the first time in the present article, SLES-CAPB-Fatty-acid mixtures are studied in detail by both rheological and cryo-TEM measurements, even though these ternary mixtures are widely used in many industrial products such as shampoos, body washes, etc. Furthermore, the results contribute to the understanding of the structure–rheology relation in mixed micellar solutions containing giant micelles. It is demonstrated that small changes in the micelle

composition and co-surfactant charge (HC8 vs NaC8), which affect the molecular packing within the micelle and the intramicellar interactions, could produce rapid growth of wormlike micelles that leads to a drastic change in both solution's rheology and microstructure. This effect could be utilized to control the physicochemical and rheological properties of surfactant formulations with applications in personal-care and house-hold detergency, including preparation of low-surfactant formulations, thus, decreasing the contamination of the environment by detergents.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Appendix A. Additional experimental and numerical results. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b03955>

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Supporting Information

for the article

Synergistic growth of giant wormlike micelles in ternary mixed surfactant solutions: Effect of octanoic acid

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Appendix A. Additional experimental and numerical results

A.1. Electrolytic conductivity measurements of TEGO® Betain F50 salt content

From the product specification data of TEGO® Betain F50 (Goldschmidt GmbH – now part of Evonik Industries AG), one can see its chemical composition: CAPB (37 – 42 wt%), NaCl (5.8 – 7.3 wt%) and water.¹ In other words, 100 mM CAPB solution contains from 81 to 120 mM NaCl. To determine the exact amount of NaCl in our batch of TEGO® Betain F50, we carried out electrolytic conductivity measurements using a conductivity meter EC 215 (Hanna Instruments – USA).

Figure S1 shows that the electrolytic conductivity κ increases as a function of CAPB concentration c_{CAPB} . At its natural $\text{pH} = 5.0 \pm 0.5$,¹ CAPB is in zwitterionic (uncharged) form, meaning that the observed increase of κ is solely due to the presence of NaCl, given by:

$$c_{\text{NaCl}} = x c_{\text{CAPB}}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where c_{NaCl} is the molar concentration of NaCl and x is the molar fraction of salt with respect to CAPB. Then, the conductivity κ of the studied solutions can be evaluated as follows:^{2,3}

$$\kappa = \kappa_0 + \Lambda_{\text{NaCl}}^{(0)} f(I) c_{\text{NaCl}}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Here, κ_0 is the background conductivity, which accounts for trace amounts of other ionic species (like H^+ , OH^- , HCO_3^-) in the water used; $\Lambda_{\text{NaCl}}^{(0)} = 126.39 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ is the molar conductivity of NaCl solution at infinite dilution;⁴ $f(I)$ is a correction coefficient for ion-ion interactions; and $I = c_{\text{NaCl}}$, expressed as $\text{mol/L} \equiv \text{M}$, is the ionic strength. The correction factor $f(I)$ reads:³

$$f(I) = 1 - 0.7\sqrt{I} + 0.74I. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Using eq A.2, we fitted the experimental data shown in Fig. S1. From the fit, κ_0 and x were determined as adjustable parameters, and are as follows: $\kappa_0 = 6.5 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, close to that of water equilibrated with CO_2 , and $x = 1.18 \pm 0.06$. In the latter value, we have taken into account that the typical error of the conductivity measurement is up to 5 %.

Figure S1. Plot of the electrolytic conductivity κ versus CAPB concentration c_{CAPB} . The full circles represent the experimental data, whereas the solid line is the fit to the data using eq A.2.

A.2. Ionization states of CAPB and HC8

First, we will discuss the ionization state of CAPB since it is a pH-sensitive molecule. As mentioned above, at $\text{pH} = 5.0$, CAPB is predominantly in zwitterionic (uncharged) form. There is only a trace amount of cationic-CAPB (c-CAPB), which can be calculated in the following way:

$$K_{\text{a,c-CAPB}} = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} a_{\text{CAPB}}}{a_{\text{c-CAPB}}} \approx \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} c_{\text{CAPB}}}{c_{\text{c-CAPB}}} \Rightarrow \frac{c_{\text{c-CAPB}}}{c_{\text{CAPB}}} = \frac{10^{-\text{pH}}}{K_{\text{a,c-CAPB}}}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Here, a_{H^+} , a_{CAPB} and $a_{\text{c-CAPB}}$ are the activities of the respective species; and $K_{\text{a,c-CAPB}}$ is the acidity constant of c-CAPB. In eq A.4, we have assumed that the activity coefficients γ_{CAPB} and $\gamma_{\text{c-CAPB}}$ are equal. For similar 1-12 carboxylate betaine, $K_{\text{a,c-CAPB}} \approx 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.⁵ Therefore, using eq A.4, we estimate that c-CAPB should be around 0.1 % at $\text{pH} = 5$ and even less at higher pH.

Second, we will estimate the degree of HC8 ionization in the mixed micelles α , consisting of CAPB, SLES and HC8. Following the approach from ref. 6, we have that:

$$\gamma_i y_i = \frac{c_i}{K_{i,\text{mic}}}, \quad (i = \text{HC8 or C8}^-). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Here, γ_i and y_i are the activity coefficient and the molar fraction of component i in the micelles, respectively; c_i is the respective monomer concentration in the bulk; and $K_{i,\text{mic}}$ is the micellization constant, which is related to the work for transferring of a monomer of component i from the solution into a micelle. Assuming that $\gamma_{\text{HC8}} \approx \gamma_{\text{C8}^-}$, from eq A.5, we obtain the relationship:

$$\frac{y_{\text{C8}^-}}{y_{\text{HC8}}} = \frac{c_{\text{C8}^-}}{c_{\text{HC8}}} \frac{K_{\text{HC8},\text{mic}}}{K_{\text{C8}^-,\text{mic}}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $K_{\text{HC8},\text{mic}} \approx 3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and $K_{\text{C8}^-,\text{mic}} \approx 0.39 \text{ M}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.⁶ These values demonstrate that the transfer of the nonionic fatty acid (HC8) from the bulk into a micelle is much more favorable (about 100 times) than the transfer of the negatively-charged carboxylate (C8^-). Additionally, from the condition for dissociation equilibrium between HC8 and C8^- in the bulk, we find that:

$$\frac{c_{\text{C8}^-}}{c_{\text{HC8}}} = \frac{K_{\text{a,HC8}}}{10^{-\text{pH}}}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where $K_{\text{a,HC8}} = 1.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ ($\text{p}K_{\text{a,HC8}} = 4.89$) is the acidity constant of HC8 at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.⁴ Combining eq A.6 and A.7, the ratio $y_{\text{C8}^-} / y_{\text{HC8}}$ yields:

$$\frac{y_{\text{C8}^-}}{y_{\text{HC8}}} = \frac{K_{\text{a,HC8}}}{10^{-\text{pH}}} \frac{K_{\text{HC8},\text{mic}}}{K_{\text{C8}^-,\text{mic}}}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Finally, the degree of HC8 ionization in the mixed micelles α is given by:

$$\alpha \equiv \frac{y_{\text{C8}^-}}{y_{\text{C8}^-} + y_{\text{HC8}}} = \frac{10^{\text{pH}-6.91}}{1 + 10^{\text{pH}-6.91}}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Figure S2a shows how the pH of the ternary micellar solution depends on the *input* HC8 concentration at fixed 70 mM CAPB and 30 mM SLES. Below 25 mM HC8, the micellar solutions are clear and their pH decreases logarithmically with the increase of HC8 concentration. At 25 mM HC8, the mixed micelles are fully-loaded with octanoic acid; hence, any excess amount of HC8 precipitates in the form of small droplets and the samples become turbid. Above 25 mM HC8, the pH levels off, because the monomer concentration c_{HC8} in the bulk is fixed to 4.2 mM, that is, the solubility of octanoic acid in water at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.⁶

Figure S2. (a) The pH of the ternary mixtures is plotted versus the *input* HC8 concentration at fixed 70 mM CAPB and 30 mM SLES. The full circles represent the experimental data, whereas the dashed line follows the observed tendency. (b) Plot of α versus the *input* HC8 concentration at fixed 70 mM CAPB and 30 mM SLES. The solid line is calculated using eq A.8.

Using the experimental data from Fig. S2a and applying eq A.8, we calculated the degree of HC8 ionization α as a function of the input HC8 concentration (Fig. S2b). In Fig. S2b, α decreases from about 4.5 % to 1.6 % and then reaches a plateau. From these numerical results, we also see that the tri-component mixed micelles contain much more nonionic HC8 than negatively-charged $C8^-$, having $y_{HC8} / y_{C8^-} > 20$, while $C8^-$ is more abundant in the bulk, having $c_{HC8} / c_{C8^-} < 0.6$. As explained before, such partitioning in the micelles is to be expected since the nonionic HC8 more readily goes in the micelles than the negatively-charged carboxylate ($C8^-$).

A.3. Effect of sodium octanoate (NaC8) on the micellar growth

To prove that HC8 (rather than NaC8) induces the micellar growth, we carried out additional experiments with NaC8. The samples were prepared following the experimental procedure from Section 3.2. Figure S3 shows the results of our pH and viscosity measurements of the respective NaC8-containing systems. We see that the pH increases logarithmically, whereas η_0 decreases linearly with the NaC8 concentration. The latter can be explained as follows: NaC8 increases the surface charge density of the mixed micelles; hence, they diminish in size due to increased intramicellar electrostatic repulsion between the negatively-charged headgroups and η_0 decreases (Figure S3).

Figure S3. The pH and zero-shear viscosity η_0 are plotted as a function of the *input* NaC8 concentration at fixed 70 mM CAPB and 30 mM SLES. The full circles represent pH data, whereas the empty diamonds represent the measured viscosity η_0 .

In contrast, the non-ionic HC8 decreases the surface charge density of the mixed micelles and serves as a spacer between the negatively-charged SLES headgroups, which leads to micellar growth; see the main text of the article.

A.4. Additional rheological results

From Table S1, we see that around the viscosity peak the relaxation time τ_R passes through a maximum, while the elastic plateau modulus G_0 increases. Similar behavior was observed previously in binary (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB, and sodium salicylate) solutions by Hoffmann & Abdel-Rahem.⁷ They have shown that at the peak η_0 is controlled by reptation, whereas away from the peak η_0 is controlled by reversible scission (kinetic control).⁷ The two mechanisms can be distinguished by addition of glycerol, which shortens τ_R under reptation control, but weakly affects τ_R under scission (kinetic) control.⁷

Table S1. Rheological properties of the studied micellar solutions around the viscosity peak at fixed total (CAPB+SLES) concentration, $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ mM.

HC8 (mM)	G_0 (Pa)	τ_R (s)	$\eta_{\omega=0}$ (Pa·s)	η_0 (Pa·s)
16	2.34	1.35	3.16	4.61
18	7.32	5.15	37.7	41.0
20	16.0	0.125	2.00	2.06

Figure S4. Effect of octanoic acid (HC8) on the sample's viscosity at fixed $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ mM (140 mM CAPB and 60 mM SLES) – data from the steady shear regime. (a) Plot of the apparent shear viscosity η vs the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$. (b) The zero-shear viscosity η_0 vs HC8 concentration.

Figure S5. Rheological data for the ternary micellar solutions at fixed HC8 concentration of 18 mM and at four different values of the total surfactant (CAPB+SLES) concentration c_{tot} . The dimensionless shear stress σ / G_0 is plotted versus the dimensionless shear rate $\tau_R \dot{\gamma}$. G_0 and τ_R are determined from the oscillatory experiments; see Section 4.2 for details. From the curves at $c_{\text{tot}} = 100$ and 200 mM, we see that the shear-banding plateau sets in at $\tau_R \dot{\gamma} \approx 2.6$ and the plateau value levels off at $\sigma / G_0 \approx 0.67$; see ref. 10 in the paper. However, at higher concentrations, $c_{\text{tot}} = 300$ and 400 mM, some deviations occur, probably due to a different regime.

Figure S6. Frequency sweep data for the ternary micellar solutions at fixed HC8 concentration of 18 mM at two values of the total surfactant (CAPB+SLES) concentration, c_{tot} . The storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' , are plotted versus the angular frequency ω . (a) $c_{\text{tot}} = 200$ mM. (b) $c_{\text{tot}} = 300$ mM. The solid lines are drawn in accordance with the pure Maxwell model.

Figure S7. Frequency sweep data for the ternary micellar solutions at fixed HC8 concentration of 18 mM at two values of the total surfactant (CAPB+SLES) concentration, c_{tot} . The Cole-Cole plots depict G''/G_{osc} vs G'/G_{osc} , where $G_{\text{osc}} = G_0/2$. The semicircle represents the pure Maxwellian behavior, whereas the solid lines represent fits of numerical data from refs. 8 and 17 in the paper.

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